

FACTORS HINDERING THE DEVELOPMENT OF «SMART» INNOVATIONS

Aliyeva Elnara Ametovna, Ph.D

Doctor of Philosophy of Economic Sciences, Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology

Abstract: The outbreak of the COVID-19 coronavirus in 2020 had a negative impact on the development of the entire global economy. However, it helped states to realistically assess their internal capabilities and potential, as well as to determine new horizons and directions for the strategy of innovative development. As a result, new business opportunities and challenges are opening up for small businesses and entrepreneurship in solving the national strategic goals of the country. The purpose of modern innovation is not only to make a profit through competitive advantage, but also to solve more noble issues and social problems. Modern innovations should be focused on the needs of society [1].

Key words: innovations, progressive innovations, "smart" innovations, purpose, tasks, factors, analysis, potential, cost, secrecy, perspective.

The goal of modern, "smart" and progressive innovations should be to ensure a high level of socio-economic and social development of the country, by ensuring the rights, guarantees and security of both the civilian population and people of all professions [1].

Their main task is to assist the state in providing and satisfying the needs of the population through the timely renewal of their activities, due to their flexibility and purposeful desire to develop and apply modern, smart innovations in all areas of the economy. According to the theory of "Evolution of technological waves", innovations inherent in the 6th wave (2010-2035) are innovations in the field of high, "smart" technologies, digitalization and contactless services. They require the joint efforts and knowledge of such specialists as biochemists, microelectronics, computer scientists, biotechnologists, genetic engineering, that is, they acquire the next level of complexity and are in the nature of "smart" technologies.

Consequently, modern small businesses and entrepreneurship should employ highly qualified specialists in their field, able not only to work efficiently, but also to carry out innovative activities that meet the requirements of the 6th wave of the theory of "Evolution of technological waves". The emergence of "smart" technologies in the market will have the effect of "disruptive" innovations, since they are not available on the market, and the global market for "smart" technologies is in its infancy.

An analysis of the activities of small businesses and entrepreneurship, as well as their products, revealed a number of factors that adversely affect the development of innovation and the development of "smart" technologies and innovations. The main ones should include:

- lack of intellectual potential. The intellectual potential of an enterprise is formed on the basis of human potential, the characteristics of which are education, qualifications, experience of employees, the ability to innovate, etc.

It is obvious that if an enterprise has employees with a high level of education, a desire for self-development and self-realization, actively raising their intellectual level, then the establishment of an innovative development vector in the enterprise will be more successful, and the process of innovation will be more effective than in an enterprise where qualitative and quantitative the composition does not meet the required level, where there is no motivation and constant staff turnover.[2] In addition, the intellectual potential as an integral part of the innovative potential of the enterprise should reflect the volume of research and development projects created at the enterprise, intellectual property objects, the volume of intangible assets of the enterprise as the results of intellectual activity.

- the lack of such innovations in the market, since the existing innovative developments in this area are at the stage of research and testing, they are not yet ready for large-scale production. As a result, there is no competition, which does not stimulate entrepreneurs in the search for innovative solutions and the implementation of innovative activities;
- secrecy of existing developments and research;
- very high cost;
- lack of vision of the prospects for the development of "smart" innovations.

It should be noted here that small businesses, due to the above reasons, are not interested in hiring highly qualified specialists. They seek to increase production and hire cheap labor, so they hire specialists with secondary and secondary specialized education. Such specialists perform physical work in the workshops and do not form the intellectual potential of the enterprise. What is the main mistake of small businesses and entrepreneurship, which is not seeing the prospects and the need for innovation. The elimination of the above barriers will help to accelerate the transition of small businesses and entrepreneurship to the implementation of innovative activities and increase the competitiveness of both enterprises and the country. Modern, progressive innovations will contribute to:

- the use of joint knowledge of specialists in various fields;
- entering completely new markets;
- creation of progressive innovations;
- taking into account the security of the population;
- creation of a platform for the development and implementation of new generation innovations [1].

Bibliography:

1. Aliyeva E. MODEL OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY // Economics and education. – 2021. – no. 5. - S. 149-155.
2. Bayboboeva, F. N. (2020). Innovation-entrepreneurial competence. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences, 8(2), 170Eournal.
3. Ustinova L.N., Sirazetdinov R.M. Innovative potential of the enterprise: essence, structure, evaluation. //Russian entrepreneurship. -2017. - Volume 18. No. 23. - P. 3751-3764

